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New Records of the Ant Species *Tetramorium walshi* (Forel, 1890) (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Taiwan, with Additional Reports of *Tetramorium* Species from Penghu Islands

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Abstract. *Tetramorium* is a highly diverse ant genus with a worldwide distribution, and 10 species of this genus have been recorded in Taiwan. In this study, *Tetramorium walshi* (Forel, 1890) is reported from Taiwan for the first time, based on specimens collected from the Penghu Islands and Kinmen Islands. Additionally, three more *Tetramorium* species are reported from the Penghu Islands for the first time, accompanied by an identification key for the *Tetramorium* species found in this region. This study provides preliminary results on the investigation of the ant fauna of Taiwan's outlying islands, aiming to address the research gap on this underexplored topic.

Keywords: Formicidae, *Tetramorium*, Penghu Islands, Taiwan, Kinmen islands

Introduction

The ant genus *Tetramorium* Mayr, 1855, commonly known as pavement ants, is a highly diverse myrmicine genus comprising 590 valid species and is distributed worldwide (Janicki et al., 2016; Guénard et al., 2017; Bolton, 2024). Generally, *Tetramorium* can be characterized by a combination of 11- or 12-segmented (mostly 12-segmented) antennae with an apically 3-segmented club, triangular mandibles with 2 or 3 apical teeth larger than the rest, a developed propodeal spine, and the lateral portions of the clypeus raised into a sharp ridge in front of the antennal insertions (Bolton, 1977; Terayama, 2009). In Taiwan, 10 species of *Tetramorium* have been recorded, including a former *Rhoptromyrmex* species, *Tetramorium wroughtonii* (Forel, 1902), which was transformed into *Tetramorium* several years ago (Terayama, 2009; Ward et al., 2015).

Currently, our understanding of the Formicidae fauna of Taiwan's outlying islands is limited, with only a few recent surveys conducted on the ant fauna of Taiwan's western outlying islands. For instance, *Dolichoderus sibiricus* Emery, 1889 was recorded from the Kinmen Islands (Hsu et al., 2017), and *Odontoponera denticulata* (Smith, 1858) was reported from Penghu Islands (Leong et al., 2017). During expeditions to Penghu Islands and subsequent specimen examinations from 2021 to 2022, I discovered a *Tetramorium* species distributed in Kinmen and Penghu Islands that is morphologically distinct from other Taiwanese members. After a detailed morphological comparison with Oriental *Tetramorium*, it was identified as *Tetramorium walshi* (Forel, 1890), representing a newly recorded species for Taiwan. Additionally, three other *Tetramorium* species collected by the author are reported from the Penghu Islands for the first time, and an identification key is also provided.

Material and methods

The specimens were preserved in 95% alcohol and stored at -20°C after collection. They were subsequently mounted as dried specimens for further morphological examination. All voucher specimens were deposited in NTU (Department of Entomology, National Taiwan University, Taipei, Taiwan). Dried specimens were examined using a Leica S9D stereomicroscope, then photographed with a Leica Z16APO microscope equipped with a Leica DMC5400 CMOS camera, with images focus-stacked using LAS software (Version 4.13.0). Photos of living ants were taken in situ using a Nikon Z6 camera equipped with an AF-S VR Micro Nikkor 105mm F/2.8G lens. All figures were editing using Adobe Lightroom Classic and WPS Presentation as needed.

Results

Family Formicidae Latreille, 1809
Subfamily Myrmicinae Lepeletier de Saint-Fargeau, 1835
Genus *Tetramorium* Mayr, 1855

***Tetramorium walshi* (Forel, 1890) 沃氏皺家蟻 (Fig. 1)**

Triglyphothrix walshi Forel, 1890: 107.

Triglyphothrix musculus Forel, 1902a: 239.

Triglyphothrix walshi spuria Forel, 1912b: 58.

Materials examined. TAIWAN: [Kinmen Co.] 5 workers, Longkou (隴口), Jinning Township, 13. VII. 2021, Kai-Ti Lin leg. (NTU); [Penghu Co.] 21 workers, Xiwen Village (西文里), Magong City, 7. XII. 2022, Kai-Wei Chan leg. (NTU).

Diagnosis. *T. walshi* can be distinguished from other Oriental species by the combination of the following characters: Head, body, and appendages with uniformly dense trifid or quadrifid hairs; node of petiole in dorsal view distinctly broader than long and strongly compressed anteroposteriorly (Bolton, 1976). In Taiwan, *T. walshi* is most similar to *T. parvispinum* and *T. lanuginosum* in having branched hairs on the body but can still be differentiated by the aforementioned characters.

Distribution. Widely distributed in the Indomalayan region, including Taiwan (new record: Kinmen Islands and Penghu Islands), India, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Thailand, Vietnam, Peninsular Malaysia, China, Philippines, Sulawesi, Java, and the Lesser Sunda Islands (Janicki et al., 2016; Guénard et al., 2017).

Remarks. This species was found in both Kinmen Islands and Penghu Islands rather in the main island of Taiwan. Minor variation on the body color was found between individuals collected from different islands; specifically, individuals from Penghu tend to be darker. However, additional morphological differences was not observed. In Penghu, *T. walshi* was found to be sympatrical with *T. lanuginosum* Mayr, 1870 and *T. smithi* Mayr, 1879, in expansive open lawns (Fig. 5A).

Fig. 1. The worker specimen of *Tetramorium walshi* (Forel, 1890). (A–C) Kinmen's specimen. (D–F) Penghu's specimen. (A, D) Head in frontal view, scale bar = 0.2 mm. (B, E) Dorsal view, scale bar = 0.5 mm. (C, F) Lateral view, scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Tetramorium lanuginosum Mayr, 1870 絨毛皺家蟻 (Fig. 2)

Tetramorium obesum striatidens Emery, 1889: 501.

Triglyphothrix ceramensis Stitz, 1912: 506.

Triglyphothrix mauricei Donisthorpe, 1946: 778.

Triglyphothrix striatidens australis Forel, 1902b: 449.

Triglyphothrix striatidens felix Forel, 1912a: 160.

Triglyphothrix striatidens flavescens Wheeler, 1929: 55.

Triglyphothrix striatidens laevidens Forel, 1900: 284.

Triglyphothrix striatidens orissana Forel, 1902a: 239.

Triglyphothrix tricolor Donisthorpe, 1948: 136.

Materials examined. TAIWAN: [Penghu Co.] 5 workers, Xiwen Village (西文里), Magong City, 7. XII. 2022, Kai-Wei Chan leg. (NTU).

Distribution. Widespread in tropical and subtropical parts of Asia, Australia, Africa, the Mediterranean, North America and the islands surrounding Oceania, Madagascar, the Galapagos, and the Eastern Caribbean (Wetterer, 2010).

Remarks. This species has long been considered a tramp species, likely originating from India and extending through tropical and subtropical East Asia to northern Australia (Wetterer, 2010). In Taiwan, it is a common species that prefers a dry environment.

Fig. 2. The worker specimen of *Tetramorium lanuginosum* Mayr, 1870 collected from Penghu. (A) Head in frontal view, scale bar = 0.2 mm. (B) Dorsal view, scale bar = 0.5 mm. (C) Lateral view, scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Tetramorium smithi Mayr, 1879 史密皺家蟻 (Fig. 3)

Tetramorium simillimum laevinode Forel, 1902a: 235.

Tetramorium smithi kanariense Forel, 1902a: 703.

Materials examined. TAIWAN: [Penghu Co.] 2 workers, Xiwen Village (西文里), Magong City, 7. XII. 2022, Kai-Wei Chan leg. (NTU); 7 workers, Chima Village (赤馬村), Xiyu Township, 8. XII. 2022, Kai-Wei Chan leg. (NTU).

Distribution. Widespread in Indomalayan region, including India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Laos, Thailand, Vietnam, China, Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, Philippines, Taiwan, Ryukyu Islands and several Micronesia Islands (Janicki et al., 2016; Guénard et al., 2017).

Remarks. Terayama (2009) recorded this species from Taiwan for the first time, but it is rarely encountered on the main island of Taiwan. I found that this species is relatively common in Penghu, where it inhabits grassland environments as a ground-dwelling ant. Additionally, the social carrying behavior of *T. smithi* between workers was observed for the first time (Fig. 5B).

Fig. 3. The worker specimen of *Tetramorium smithi* Mayr, 1879 collected from Penghu. (A) Head in frontal view, scale bar = 0.2 mm. (B) Dorsal view, scale bar = 0.5 mm. (C) Lateral view, scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Tetramorium bicarinatum (Nylander, 1846) 雙脊皺家蟻 (Fig. 4)

Myrmica bicarinata Nylander, 1846: 1061.

Myrmica cariniceps Guérin-Ménéville, 1852: 79.

Myrmica kollari Mayr, 1853: 283.

Myrmica modesta Smith, 1860: 108.

Myrmica reticulata Smith, 1862: 33.

Materials examined. TAIWAN: [Penghu Co.] 6 workers, Aimen Village (隘門村), Huxi Township, 7. XII. 2022, Kai-Wei Chan leg. (NTU).

Distribution. Widely distributed throughout tropical and subtropical regions of both the Old and New Worlds, including continental areas and islands surrounding Africa, the Caribbean, and Oceania (Wetterer, 2009).

Remarks. This species has long been recognized as a tramp species and is considered one of the most widely distributed ant species, presumably originating in the Indo-Pacific (Wetterer, 2009). In Taiwan, it is commonly found in various types of habitats. Unlike three other ground-living *Tetramorium* species in the Penghu Islands, *T. bicarinatum* was active on trees and was observed feeding on nectar (Fig. 5C).

Fig. 4. The worker specimen of *Tetramorium bicarinatum* (Nylander, 1846) collected from Penghu. (A) Head in frontal view, scale bar = 0.5 mm. (B) Dorsal view, scale bar = 0.5 mm. (C) Lateral view, scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Fig. 5. (A) Habitat inhabited by *Tetramorium walshi*, *T. lanuginosum*, and *T. smithi*. (B) Social carrying behavior between workers of *T. smithi*. (C) *T. bicarinatum* feeding on nectar.

Discussion

This study presents a preliminary investigation into the ant fauna of Taiwan's outlying islands, specifically the Penghu Islands, addressing a research gap in this underexplored area of myrmecology. Four *Tetramorium* species are recorded in Penghu: two tramp species with global distribution and two Indomalayan species. Among the Indomalayan species, *T. smithi* appears to be more abundant in the Penghu Islands compared to the main island of Taiwan. In contrast, *T. walshi* is found in the Penghu Islands but not on the main island of Taiwan, displaying a distribution pattern similar to that of *Meranophus bicolor* and *Odontoponera denticulata* (Wheeler, 1930b; Leong et al., 2017). These findings suggest the biogeographical significance and environmental uniqueness of the Penghu Islands, emphasizing the need for further myrmecological investigations of Taiwan's outlying islands.

Key to *Tetramorium* species of Penghu Islands

澎湖產皺家蟻屬物種檢索表

1. Hairs on head, mesosoma, and petiole abundant and with branched ones
 頭部、中軀與腹柄節上的體毛豐富，且具分岔的體毛.....2
 - Hairs on head, mesosoma, and petiole sparse and not branched
 頭部、中軀與腹柄節上的體毛稀疏且不分岔.....3
2. Dorsal view of petiolar node not broader than long; Hairs on first gastral tergite sparse, either non-branched or bifid; Body bicolor, head and mesosoma brown to dark brown with blackish brown gaster.
 背面觀時，腹柄節瘤部寬度不大於長度；腹錘第一節背板上的體毛稀疏，不分岔或二分岔；體軀雙色，頭部與中軀褐色至深褐色，腹錘黑褐色。.....*Tetramorium lanuginosum* 絨毛皺家蟻
 - Dorsal view of petiolar node apparently broader than long; Hairs on first gastral tergite abundant, either trifid or quadrifid; Body concolor, generally blackish brown.
 背面觀時，腹柄節瘤部寬度明顯大於長度；腹錘第一節背板上的體毛豐富，三分岔或四分岔；體軀同色，整體為黑褐色。.....*Tetramorium walshi* 沃氏皺家蟻
3. Antenna with 11 segments; Dorsal of petiole and postpetiole smooth and without sculpture.
 觸角 11 節；腹柄節與後腹柄節背部光滑無刻紋。.....*Tetramorium smithi* 史密皺家蟻
 - Antenna with 12 segments; Dorsal of petiole and postpetiole sculptured.
 觸角 12 節；腹柄節與後腹柄節背部具刻紋。.....*Tetramorium bicarinatum* 雙脊皺家蟻

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沃氏皺家蟻於臺灣地區的新紀錄暨附澎湖產皺家蟻屬之補充紀錄

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摘要: 皺家蟻(*Tetramorium*)是一個全球廣布且物種多樣的屬，目前已在臺灣記錄到 10 個物種。本研究基於採集自澎湖群島和金門群島的標本，首次在臺灣地區記錄到沃氏皺家蟻(*Tetramorium walshi* (Forel, 1890))。此外，本研究還報導了三種皺家蟻在澎湖群島的新分布紀錄，並提供了澎湖地區皺家蟻屬的物種檢索表。這些發現為臺灣離島螞蟻相提供了初步的調查結果，以期填補離島螞蟻研究的空白。

關鍵詞: 蟻科、皺家蟻屬、澎湖群島、臺灣、金門群島